

DIGITAL ECONOMY AND ITS IMPACT ON SOCIETY**Melikuzieva Zunnura Avazjon qizi**

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Annotation: This thesis sheds light on the digital economy and its impact on society, as well as on how society can significantly improve the standard of living of its citizens, and that this is its main advantage.

Key words: digital qt history, digital technologies, progress, system, Internet economy, CRM, Fidbeck, budget allocation.

Introduction. In many developed countries, the digital economy has had a significant impact on the factors of their development. This is reflected in the fact that the role of the digital economy in the life of society is growing every day. We are witnessing how the concept of "digital economy" has been applied many times recently.

- ✓ so, in our article we will try to tell you in detail about the digital economy.
- ✓ what is the digital economy in our article?
- ✓ and how to describe it?
- ✓ what are its advantages?

About the tasks and goals of the digital economy, what are the obstacles to the development of the digital economy in Uzbekistan?

We will try to answer such important questions as in the Message of the President of the country Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Senate and the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis, 2020 was declared the Year of Science, Education and the Digital Economy. After that, citizens began to have numerous questions about the term "digital economy".

They: What is the digital economy? and how can it be described?

1. The digital economy is a system of economic, social and cultural relations based on the use of digital technologies. Sometimes it is also called internet economy, new economy or web economy.

2. The digital economy is the conduct of economic activity in which the main factor in the production and provision of services is information in the form of numbers, and with the help of processing large amounts of information and analyzing the result of this processing, solutions are implemented that are more effective than the previous system in the production, maintenance, technologies, devices, storage, delivery of products of various types.

3. Digital economy is an activity related to the development of digital computer technologies in the provision of online services, electronic payments, online commerce, crowdfunding and other activities.

4. The digital economy is an economic activity closely related to e-business and e-commerce, based on digital technologies, as well as a set of digital goods and services produced and sold as a result of this activity.

5. Digital Economy -also referred to by the terms Internet economy, new economy or web economy.

Brief definition: The digital economy is an electronic state of activity that requires less effort from a person, less costs than before, and is able to show the result of accurate accounting. If we look at the digital economy, trade and e-commerce, we will see that when a person feels the need for an item and chooses it directly on the market and buys it for cash, it will be a traditional economy. Now he chooses the goods to his liking through telegram or a similar online store, pays money to the owner of the goods through an electronic payment system and receives the goods through a delivery service-the so-called digital economy. This is an explanation of the problem using the simplest example. The digital economy is not some other economy that needs to be created from scratch. This means moving the existing economy into a new system by creating new technologies, platforms and business models and implementing them into everyday life.

In a sense, we are all already in the digital economy, taking advantage of its amenities. As an example, we can say that our salaries come on plastic cards, we pay for utilities, telephone, Internet and other products and services using electronic payment, file a tax return electronically, transfer money from card to card, order food at home, etc. Advantages of the digital economy it was found that interest in the digital economy, modern technologies and platforms, clients with partners and government organizations help businesses and individuals to reduce costs by minimizing personal communication.

As a result, his changes in society and the economy have grown significantly. This made it possible to establish interaction quickly, accurately and easily. The result was a network, digital or electronic economy based on resources.

Of course, it is natural that the development of information and communication technologies, the introduction of modern technologies into our lives gives many positive opportunities in the life of every person. The development of digital technologies allows a person and him to use the necessary service faster, save a lot of money by buying the necessary products cheaply via the Internet. At the same time, the consumer can become an entrepreneur himself, engage in online sales without leaving home.

For example, buying any magazine in electronic form can cost you much cheaper than buying the same magazine in printed form. Other advantages of the development of the digital economy may be:

- improving the efficiency of work in production;
- improving the competitiveness of companies;
- reduction of production costs;
- creation of new jobs;
- the emergence of new modern professions;
- overcoming poverty and overcoming social inequality.

These are just some of the advantages of the digital economy. The development of the digital economy is the reason that it makes our daily life more efficient, can provide additional opportunities and stimulate the growth and development of the market. Digitalization, in fact, is a new term and implies the involvement of IT solutions in the innovative process of management and office management, as a result of which information technologies are used in all systems, from a simple electronic counter to electronic government. The digital segment of the economy includes public administration, consulting and information services, the defense system, finance, wholesale and retail trade, as well as the service sector, which accounts for more than 70% of the GDP of developed countries.

Based on our research, the WDC rating methodology divides digital competitiveness into three main factors: - knowledge - technology - readiness for the future of the world's countries with a developed digital economy, Norway, Sweden and Switzerland are considered "digital" countries today. The 10 countries with advanced digital economies include the United States, Great Britain, Denmark, Finland, Singapore, South Korea and Hong Kong. In turn, each of these factors is divided into 3 sub-factors that highlight each aspect of the analyzed areas.

IMD World Digital Competitiveness Ranking 2022-Overview fighting Cyber threats and appeasing digital users: Go beyond R&D to enable digitization The data-driven digital economy is characterized by a large imbalance: only 20 percent of people in less developed countries use the Internet; when they do, it usually happens at a relatively low download speed and a relatively high price. the tab is attached. This limits opportunities to participate and benefit from the emerging data-driven digital economy.

Thus, the division associated with the data is added to the traditional numerical division. The higher the diversification and dynamics of the economy, the greater the unique information turnover within and outside the country and the greater the information traffic within national economies. That is why the digital economy is developing rapidly in markets where the number of participants is large and IT services

are widespread. This is especially true for those industries that are actively working with the Internet – transport, trade, logistics, and the like. According to some researchers, the share of the electronic segment in them is close to 10% of GDP, providing employment for 4% of the population. More importantly, these indicators are steadily growing. It is obvious that the effectiveness of the digital economy is influenced not only by the scale of information technology and the availability of infrastructure, but also by standard economic criteria such as the business environment, human capital and tools for successful management. Consequently, economic progress is based on them, which means that these criteria play as important a role in the development of the digital economy as before.

The digital economy is being created before our eyes, old and new companies using IT tools to create new services and business models around the world are creating strong competition for companies that are leaders in most industries. According to forecasts, in the coming years, macroeconomics will strongly depend on manufacturers who will rely on the criteria of "lean production", additive, nano- and biotechnological. In this regard, the volume of information considered necessary for rational management is also increasing, while the management structure of production and civil communication, business and government agencies is undergoing significant changes.

As the main prerequisites and factors for gradually entering the path of socio-economic progress, it specifies the following:

- implementation of e-government and digital city concepts through the integration of informatization and public administration bodies, as well as municipal services;
- gross production of new technological generation products (for example, self-driving cars, etc.);
- implementation of ideas for the construction of "smart" and eco-friendly houses using original finishes and building materials;

- widely promote alternative forms of employment through outsourcing, self-employment, etc.;
- create professional networks that serve to find freelancers to perform certain tasks.

All of the above allows businesses to reduce costs with the help of modern platforms on which goods and electronic services are integrated into production and management. First of all, this issue concerns the integration of ordering services, sharing resources, choosing counterparties, conducting electronic commerce, payments and much more. The technological digital environment is an "aquarium" in which legal entities and individuals establish a completely new dialogue for joint activities. Information technologies allow enterprises to master completely new, more intensive work rates and diversify the form of services and products. In addition, researchers talk about the appearance of products with a short shelf life on the market.

What benefits can we derive from the digital economy for the development of our society? The digital economy significantly increases the standard of living of people, which is its main advantage. The digital economy is the main trump card of corruption and the "black economy". Because numbers seal everything, store it in memory, quickly provide information when you need it. In such conditions, it is impossible to hide any information, make secret deals, not give complete information about a particular activity, the computer will show it all.

The abundance of data and systematicity do not allow lies and fraud, since it is impossible to deceive the system. How developed is the digital economy in Uzbekistan? It is worth noting that today users actively use Telegram bots to order food. Various online stores and electronic payment systems are also actively developing.

Consequently, our citizens believe in electronic transactions. Only to this day, users make small transactions that do not require large expenses, while they are less willing to increase the average volume of purchases. Now the issue is to develop the implementation of medium and large economic transactions and financial transactions

using digital technologies. How developed is the digital economy in Uzbekistan? It is worth noting that today users actively use Telegram bots to order food. Various online stores and electronic payment systems are also actively developing.

Consequently, our citizens believe in electronic transactions. Only to this day, users make small transactions that do not require large expenses, while they are less willing to increase the average volume of purchases. Now the issue is to develop the implementation of medium and large economic transactions and financial transactions using digital technologies. The foundations that can stimulate development as the President of our country Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted, in order to achieve progress, it is necessary and necessary to acquire digital knowledge and modern information technologies. This gives us the opportunity to take the shortest path of ascent. “The National Agency for Project Management under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the authorized body in the field of implementation and development of the digital economy. In addition, the Ministries of Economy, Finance, information technology, Justice and a number of other government agencies have their own responsibilities and tasks for the development of the digital economy. This was particularly noted in the Message of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Senate and the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis. Digital economy in Uzbekistan the digital economy is developing in Uzbekistan, as well as in other countries of the world.

After the introduction of information technology into our daily lives, numerous opportunities open up for ordinary people. Currently, we can order a variety of products and dishes from the comfort of home to deliver them to our home. But it is worth noting that the digital economy in Uzbekistan is developing several times slower than the potential of Uzbekistan. That is, there is a chance, there are the necessary resources, but development is much slower.

A number of obstacles to the development of the digital economy in Uzbekistan can be cited as reasons.

- monopoly in many industries;
- low internet speed and its poor quality;

- lagging legislation in the field of information technology from time to time;
- extremely low computer literacy of citizens;
- non-transparency of legislation;
- lack of specialists in the field of information technology or their departure to other countries;
- low information culture, low information hygiene;
- poor information technology security;
- the absence of specialists in the management bodies who understand the industry, or (for some) their complete absence;
- slowness (or stagnation in development) of the development of science and especially the exact sciences.

If the above issues are solved in stages, systematically, based on world experience, Uzbekistan also has a developed digital economy cybersecurity is an important condition of the digital economy in Uzbekistan, all systems are digitized. Today, you can pay bills without leaving home, receive distance learning without any problems, use the largest libraries in the world and even work. Digital services have a number of advantages over traditional ones, such as the absence of paperwork, formalities, and time savings. For example, if you receive government services digitally, you are given a discount of 10% of the set fee. All this is a sign that the transition to the digital economy is actively underway in our country. Cybersecurity is another factor in the development of the digital economy. In the conditions of quarantine in the global network, there have been cases of the spread of viruses that disable software systems, under the label "instructions for protection against coronavirus".

Financial fraudsters who tricked ordinary people into transferring money in advance to an account, promising to sell and deliver medicines online abroad, used fake online stores, websites, social media accounts and email addresses. This also confirms the need to ensure information security. Digital technologies and risks the most active driver of the digital economy is the state. He is the main customer and

consumer of the digital economy. For example, China has spent about \$9 billion for these purposes.

Alibaba's Internet resource with a market capitalization of more than \$ 210 billion proved the correctness of the direction of these investments. A state that wants to get the most out of digitalization should create a market for the necessary high-tech products and support it. At the same time, while simultaneously developing private applications for public administration, key industries and enterprises, it is also important to maintain tools that control the main platforms of the electronic economy. In particular,

Japan, although it has purchased technology, has missed out on leading positions in the digital economy due to the inability to create its own production networks in this direction and maintain the level of technical developments at a consistently high level. South Korea, on the other hand, invests in e-government and e-mediation (for e-commerce activities and public tender procurement) an amount equivalent to 1% of the national budget, generating \$10-15 billion annually and receiving income that covers expenses by 30-40 times. In particular, this result was achieved through the creation of call centers in the public and private sectors, the creation of mobile applications and the reengineering of public Internet platforms. Training of personnel working with public administration information systems remains one of the most important areas in this area. For example, in the 70s of the last century, special mobile groups of specialists were created in Belgium (including with the involvement of teachers and students of specialized educational institutions), who train government officials and configure systems directly for them in the workplace.

In short, at a time when "digital inequality is the midwife of inequality," digitalization of all sectors of the economy is a key condition for integration into the world community, gaining its place in the world market, economic prosperity, and creating amenities for the population. Fortunately, this is the main issue on the agenda in our country. Uzbekistan inspires brave people in the field of digitalization.

List of used literature:

1. “Shavkat Mirziyoyev declared 2020 the Year of Science, Education and Development of the Digital Economy.” Dayro (January 24, 2020). Verified April 7, 2023.

2. “Video: Message of Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis”. Dayro (January 24, 2020). Verified April 7, 2023.

Links:

- What is the digital economy?
- What does the digital economy give us?